

THE MEDICINAL EFFECT OF THE SARSABIL PLANT IN DERMATOLOGICAL DISEASES AND COSMETOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223509>

Akbarov Asliddin

5 th year student of

Samarkand State Medical University

Matkarimova Gulnaz

Samarkand State Medical University

Assistant of the Department of Medical biology and genetics

Abstract

Sarsabil has been widely used in medicine in the Mediterranean region since ancient times. Medicinal sarsabil, which grows in Samarkand, Bukhara, Fergana and Tashkent regions of Uzbekistan, previously belonged to aphrodisiac plants, despite its low nutritional value, sarsabil is very rich in various elements, vitamin additional active substances, potassium and vitamin A, trace elements necessary for the health of skin, nails and hair fibers, as well as saponins, coniferin, succinic and chelidonic acids are found in the plant. Sarsabil buds contain a lot of asparagine and arginine, a small amount of carotene, lysine in medicine, sarsabil has diuretic and relaxing, analgesic, antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory and anti-edematous properties. In addition, it strengthens the formation of blood, stimulates the formation of blood cells and helps in anemia. Sarsabil extract has a high effect on the nervous system and activates mental functions, expands the walls of blood vessels, lowers arterial blood pressure, improves the functioning of the liver and kidneys, stimulates the immune system and the digestive system. All these and other medicinal properties of Sarsabil have been used by mankind for centuries in various therapeutic practices. Today, most of them have been confirmed in laboratory experiments on animals, and some in clinical studies involving humans.

Key words

Immunity, trace elements, sarsabil, extract, therapeutic, asparagine, medicinal, biochemical, research, dermatological,

Introduction: Coumarin and saponin found in many plants are present in sorghum, and asparagine in the roots of the plant was first isolated from medicinal sorghum. They have a positive effect on the human body. Sarsabil extracts in capsules, tablets and other forms of domestic and foreign manufacturers are freely available along with other herbal supplements with biologically active components.

The instructions for them recommend the use of sarsabil drugs as an adaptogen, immunomodulator, diuretic, tonic and cleansing agent.

Nutritionists specializing in eco-nutrition "recommend" sarsabil for the treatment of liver, prostate, bladder, kidneys, as well as diabetes, gout, atherosclerosis and heart pathologies. In folk medicine, sarsabil rhizomes are used in the early stages of hypertension and venous insufficiency. In addition, it is prescribed to create a diuretic effect and eliminate inflammation of the urinary tract. To reduce toothache, doctors recommend chewing pieces of fresh sarsabil root. However, often the raw material obtained from the underground part of the plant is used in the form of decoctions and tinctures.

To make a tincture of sarsabil roots, they usually take a tablespoon of dried raw material in a glass of boiling water. When preparing the decoction, the same amount of raw materials is poured into 1.5 cups of water, they are first boiled, and then kept on low heat for another 2 minutes. To prepare a decoction of the herb, you need 2 tablespoons of dry raw materials and half a liter of water. The herb is first boiled for 5 minutes, then left to cool.

Drink half a glass three times a day. Although many of the medicinal effects of the underground and above-ground parts of the plant are the same, there is a certain tradition of using sarsabil decoctions and tinctures in the treatment of diseases in folk medicine. Tinctures of sarsabil rhizomes are used in kidney stone disease, nephrolithiasis, difficulty urinating, cystitis, epilepsy, and tachycardia. In the second case, dry grass (2 teaspoons) is added to a still hot decoction of roots (350 ml) and closed for 2 hours. This tool is taken 2 tablespoons 3 times a day before meals to restore heart rhythm.

Sarsabil is a popular topic of pharmaceutical and medical scientific research today, one of the reasons for this is the wide and effective use of sarsabil in folk medicine in different countries, this plant has an excellent reputation as a universal remedy. Today, scientists are actively testing the many therapeutic properties that sarsabil is famous for. And one of the most popular is the topic of the effect of sarsabil extract on brain activity and the state of the nervous system.

The effect of Sarsabil extract on memory and acetylcholinesterase activity in the scopolamine-induced amnesia model was studied in an experiment with 60 mice divided into 6 groups. Three of them received low (1.6 ml/kg), medium (8 ml/kg) and high (16 ml/kg) doses of the extract.

The results showed that the moderate dose significantly improved cognitive impairment in mice in the novel object recognition test and several other tests. Analysis of biochemical parameters confirmed behavioral parameters and showed

that sarsabil stem extract protects learning and memory function in mice by increasing cholinergic nervous system activity.

Perhaps such an extract can prevent cognitive impairment in age-related diseases such as Alzheimer's disease. Fermented sarsabil extracts reduce mental stress and improve sleep efficiency in healthy older men under psychological stress. Medicinal sarsabil extract and tincture in dermatological diseases shows its high efficiency effect in acne and many other skin diseases in adults.

REFERENCES:

1. Karimov V., Shomakhmudov A. Medicinal plants used in folk medicine and modern science. Tashkent: NMB named after Ibn Sina, 1993.
2. Usmonkhodzhayev A., Bositkhonova E. I. The genius of Ibn Sina Journal "Salomat bo'ling" 2017.
3. Usmonkhodzhayev A., Bositkhonova E. I., Pratov O'. P., Djabborov A. Etymological modern encyclopedia of medicinal plants growing in Uzbekistan Tashkent: new century generation 2018.
4. M. A. Jorayeva. Atlas of medicinal plants Tashkent: publisher 2019.
5. M. Makhsumov., Kh. Aliyev., S. Saidov., Sh. Makhsumov. Tashkent: science and technology 2013.
6. Akbarov A. T., Samiyeva G. U. Innovative approach to the current problems of medicine Andijan 2023.
7. Akbarov A. T., Samiyeva G. U. Fundamental practical medicine and pharmacy achievements in Samarkand 2023.